

THE US PROMOTION OF DEMOCRACY IN THE WANA REGION: MYTH VS. REALITY

Abul Kalam

Research Scholar, Centre for West Asian Studies
School of International Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University
Email: abul41355@gmail.com

Abstract

The United States' promotion of democracy in the West Asia and North Africa (WANA) region has long been a subject of debate, characterised by contradictions between rhetoric and practice. This study examines the evolution of US foreign policy in the WANA region across four key periods: the Cold War, post-Cold War liberalisation, post-9/11, and the post-Arab Spring era. While the US has publicly championed democratic ideals, its actions often prioritised strategic interests, such as energy security and counterterrorism, over genuine democratic reforms. The analysis highlights instances of US support for authoritarian regimes, military interventions, and the undermining of democratically elected governments, as seen in Syria, Iran, Bahrain, Afghanistan, and Iraq. The study concludes that externally imposed democracy lacks sustainability and that the US approach has frequently exacerbated instability rather than fostering democratic governance. The findings underscore the tension between America's ideological commitments and its geopolitical priorities in the WANA region.

Keywords: *US foreign policy, democracy promotion, WANA region, authoritarianism, geopolitical interests*

Introduction

The West Asia and North Africa (WANA) region is a vital and vast energy source of oil and hydrocarbons, with the world's highest reserves. American foreign policy always sees the WANA region as its core interest, as it imports oil and hydrocarbons. Ideally, American

democracy promotion encourages governmental and non-governmental actors to pursue political reforms, as many people hope will ultimately lead to democratic governance. As far as democracy promotion is concerned in the region, the American foreign policy throughout the Cold War primarily focused on containing Communist influence, trying to limit the presence and impact of the USSR and the region's security and stability. After the Second World War, America dominated and constantly interfered in the region's internal and external affairs. The WANA region is an area of the world that is vital to American interests; despite America's claim of being a "Champion of Freedom and Democracy," its close allies in the WANA region are deeply entrenched in non-democratic and authoritarian rule. To understand the US promotion of democracy in the region, very briefly first, we must understand the US Foreign Policy in four periods-

- 1- The Cold War Period from 1945-1989
- 2- The Political Liberalisation or the Post-Cold War Period from 1990-2001
- 3- The Post 9/11 Period from 2001-2010
- 4- The Democracy Era Period from 2011 to the Present

Between 1945 and 1989, US foreign policy focused on promoting stability, maintaining the status quo, and reinforcing authoritarian, repressive rule in the WANA region. After the disintegration of the USSR and the end of the Cold War, from 1990 to 2001, the balance shifted in favor of increasing the role of civil society and political opening in some parts of the WANA region. However, the 9/11 attacks on the US shockingly changed and reversed its foreign policy to support repressive regimes to secure cooperation in the so-called "war on terror." At the same time, the US invaded Afghanistan in 2001 to confront and topple the Taliban regime, which later harboured the al-Qaeda terror network in the region and abroad. The Next year, the invasion of Iraq in 2003 was based on the wrong assumption, which intended to destroy Weapons of Mass Destruction (WMD), but later it was not found. Under the same assumption, the US administration intended to promote democracy, but America could not bring about a democratic change in Iraq, which tried to impose it from the outside. However, Tunisian and Egyptian protesters took to the streets against long-standing military

dictators. It successfully brought democracy to their respective countries, unleashing unprecedented protests in the region. However, democracy only successfully survived in Tunisia, under the Ennahda, while in Egypt, it was reversed within a year with a military dictatorship. The US perception of democracy promotion has been shaped partly by the UN assessments of the region, such as the Arab Human Development Report 2002, which suggests more freedom and democracy. However, US efforts and interventions to save freedom and democracy have generally limited the UN's political role in the region.

The UN Arab Human Development Report on Freedom was written by Arab intellectuals and published in 2004. The report's main thrust was freedom and democratic governance in the Arab world. The UN Report further stressed that freedom and democracy are essential to the development and healthy society in Arab countries: It states, "No Arab thinker today doubts that freedom is a vital and necessary condition, though not the only one, for a new Arab renaissance, or that the Arab world's capacity to face up to its internal and external challenges, depends on ending tyranny and securing fundamental rights and freedoms."

America's efforts for democracy promotion in the WANA region are generally characterised by 'top-down and 'bottom-up' democratisation strategies, which can be pursued simultaneously. The top-down strategy is where the American military installed a democratic government either for pressure or, on most occasions, a military coup or direct intervention. In the case of Iraq, for example, the country was invaded by American military forces in 2003 under the pretext of having Weapons of Mass Destruction (WMD). However, WMD was not found after the invasion. Many critics have argued that in the history of the United States, presidents have used the idea of democracy promotion to justify military intervention and help the local military elite overthrow democratically elected leaders. The bottom-up strategy is where the US funds international organisations, including NGOS, to help build a base for a gradual democratic transition. This is mainly in the issue of the rule of law, accountable and transparent government institutions, and expanded political competition among different groups. This gradual democratic transition is also helped by offering technical assistance and training to the political parties and electoral bodies. It engages with civil society members, provides assessments, and promotes female participation. In the context of the WANA region, directing the US promotion of

democracy through international NGOs stems from suspicion of the motives of the US government.

Professor Paul W. Drake (2009) argued that the US first attempted to export democracy in Latin America through intervention from 1912 to 1932. Drake argued that this was contradictory because international law defines intervention as “dictatorial interference in the affairs of another state to alter the condition of things.” Albrecht Schnabel (2003) argues that there is a dilemma in the WANA region where one side has a robust authoritarian regime, and the other side has a weak civil society. He identified some difficulties, such as the strong civil society required to produce leaders and mobilise the public around democratic duties. However, it is necessary first to allow freedom of expression to create a democratic environment and a strong civil society.

Schnabel further argued that external support may be required if domestic capacities are lacking. However, external support for creating fragile yet somewhat functioning institutions is necessary. Here, the external support is meant to trigger the momentum needed to encourage the evolution of a functioning civil society. The WANA region’s democratisation must come from both below and above simultaneously. The pressure from below will be pointless if the political leadership and elites oppose reform. In contrast, top-down reform and effort are not fruitful if the political culture is underdeveloped. By focusing on funding civil society organisations, foreign donors can create dependency at the expense of building a domestic democratic movement. The state may or can use and even misuse foreign funding and aid to justify cracking down on activists and democracy proponents, as Saad Eddin Ibrahim and Ayman Nour (2007) explained in the case of Egypt.

The second dilemma for the US promotion of democracy is aid prioritisation. The priorities of Western aid, including the US, must be viewed as a whole. Therefore, there is a question about the vast amounts of money spent on military assistance than democratic aid. For example, massive foreign aid to countries like Jordan and Egypt allows regimes to co-opt and repress their populations. The state supports state job and economic infrastructures by aiding and funding state security apparatuses. These results often contradict the US positions on promoting democracy, with Effectiveness Aid Prioritisation: Military versus Democracy promotion.

A report commissioned by USAID determined that the DG (Democracy and Governance) assistance was allocated to countries in the WANA region between 1990 and 2004.

- Algeria (\$3.7 million in 8 years),
- Bahrain (\$1.3 million in 2 years),
- Egypt (\$334.3 million in 14 years),
- Iraq (\$523.6 million in 3 years),
- Jordan (\$28.3 million in 5 years),
- Lebanon (\$28.5 million in 11 years),
- Morocco (\$3.6 million in 7 years),
- Oman (\$0.6 million in 2 years),
- Qatar (\$0.8 million in 1 year),
- Saudi Arabia (\$0.4 million in 1 year),
- Tunisia (\$11.2 million in 5 years),
- Turkey (\$0.9 million in 4 years),
- West Bank and Gaza (\$155.4 million in 11 years),
- Yemen (\$6.6 million in 8 years)

In 2017, The Economist reported that the Near East Regional Democracy Program (NERDP) had allocated about \$30 million per year to promote democracy and human rights in Iran. However, most of the USAID is spent on military equipment, supporting the regime's security, and significantly less on the welfare of the ordinary people. The USAID has not even helped civil society members to make a positive discourse on democracy. The USAID has proved to play a negative role and is still blocking or hindering the transition to democracy. It has been found that these aids are used, abused, and misused by regimes to suppress the opposition and put them behind bars. Egypt, Jordan, and other countries are good examples of this.

The US Promotion of Democracy After the 9/11, 2001 Attack

After the September 11, 2001, Attack, many American scholars assumed that democratic transition was essential to regional stability and international security. Marina Ottaway (2003) argues that after the 2001 attack on the US, the Bush administration, for the first time, thought

about the promotion of democracy in the WANA region. Many US officials had also suggested and focused that most of the countries in the WANA region and their regimes' authoritarianism had produced frustration among their people. This frustration against the regimes turned in favour of militancy, political violence, and even terrorism, which challenged the security of the region and the world. However, the sudden and uncertain talk about democracy promotion by the US triggered a very negative reaction from Arab intellectuals, commentators, and journalists, including the Arab press. Many say there was very little about democracy and its future problems.

Many Arab intellectuals questioned the US intentions and accused the Bush Administration of misusing the "idea of democracy promotion" as a code word for regime change. Arab press also reacted very negatively when Colin Powell, Secretary of State under President George W. Bush, announced a conciliatory Middle East Partnership Initiative (MEPI) in December 2002, which talked about democratisation as a gradual change that the US would encourage by promoting economic development, education, rights for women and funding for civil society.

It was a shock for the Arabs when the Bush administration announced that the lack of democracy in the WANA region was not only a threat to the regime and its citizens but also to US security and its interests in the region. In many statements, Bush administration officials had linked the absence and lack of democracy, which breeds frustration and causes terrorism in their own country and outside. However, the reality was different, where terrorists were more directed against the US rather than their government in the absence of democracy in their home country. The Bush administration's new focus was on the lack of democracy as a cause of terrorism and criticised Saudi Arabia and Egypt, which had most of the terrorists involved in the 2001 attack on the US.

The Bush administration emphasised the necessity of regime change in Iraq and Palestine. However, as usual, officials had never clearly mentioned democracy promotion with regime change in the case of Iraq and Palestine. In these two cases, the US administration's position has been clear. The first step towards democracy in Iraq was to remove Saddam Hussein from power, and genuine reform in the Palestinian territory was to ensure that Yasser Arafat would not run for office and win again. US President George W. Bush and National Security Advisor

Condoleezza Rice had also stated that “changes in Iraq would lead to a far-reaching transformation of the entire region.” In an interview given to the Financial Times on 23rd September 2002, Rice declared that the “United States was committed not only to the removal of Saddam Hussein but also to the democratisation or the ‘March of Freedom’ in the Muslim world.” However, a Jordanian daily, Al-Dustour, replied to Rice’s statement, “She is ignoring. More than one and a half billion Muslims suffer from American greed and oppression, and it’s a cruel, visible war against Islam and Muslims.” Michael Ledeen (2003), a neo-conservative close to the administration and a scholar at the American Enterprise Institute, wrote about the American democracy promotions, “We should be talking about using all our political, moral and military genius to support a vast democratic revolution to liberate all the people of the Middle East from tyranny.”

The US Promotion of Democracy After Arab Uprising

The ‘Arab Uprisings’ started in Tunisia, but very soon erupted and spread across the Arab countries. Massive demonstrations happened in Egypt against Hosni Mubarak. The tumultuous uprisings in 2011 brought down a 30-year military regime. The walls in Cairo, painted colourfully, said that “the revolution has not changed the regime, but it has changed the people (Amin, 2016). For the Egyptian people, the incidents of uprising and protest were a kind of rupture to the normal life of the society, where a regime had survived through the art of repression.

In the years after the Arab Spring, euphoria turned to dysphoria as the aspirations of the youthful protesters were usurped by resurgent authoritarianism, civil wars, and terrorist groups. Tunisia was the only Arab Spring country where the uprisings helped foster democracy. A sense of resignation took hold in Washington, accompanied by the belief that autocracy no longer looked so bad compared to the chaos that has engulfed the region since 2011. For the many US policymakers who harboured deep scepticism about the prospects for democracy in the Arab world, the aftermath of the Arab Spring was a self-fulfilling prophecy. To be sure, amidst the disorder of the post-2011 period, many Arabs supported uprisings and felt nostalgic for the certainty of authoritarianism.

The Arab Spring presented entirely new opportunities for the promotion of US democracy. Perhaps for the first time, as Samuel P. Huntington

(1991) describes, the third wave of democratisation appeared as a possibility in a region that had resisted previous “waves” of democratic change sweeping the globe. Mahmood Monshipouri and Ali Assareh (2011) argued in their article titled “*New Middle East and the United States*” *What Expect After Uprising?*” that change, transformation, and overthrow of the autocratic regimes in the WANA region had resulted from the bottom-up, indigenous, antiestablishment and popular movement that has exposed the flaws in the US foreign policy. The Arab uprising had also exposed the vulnerability and weakened the state’s security apparatus, even after receiving enough USAID. The Arab uprising brought two new leaders to Egypt and Tunisia and had a partial transition towards democracy, although not completely.

After the protests in Tunisia and Egypt erupted, later in other parts of the Arab world, millions of Arabs took to the streets to demand more freedom and an end to repression. In Washington, the dilemma was no longer over whether and how much to force Arab governments to open the political space here. Conversely, the US never meaningfully challenged the durability of his rule, which was essentially the policy pursued under Bush. However, later, some space had opened in new and dramatic ways. The main agent of change was neither an Islamist nor a US but a relatively young Arab who called for an end to dictatorship and more freedom. In some cases, they succeeded, such as in Tunisia and Egypt. On the other side, the US faced a dilemma in their foreign policy choices: whether to support the protesters or put pressure on their autocratic allies to a process of democratic change with uncertain outcomes. Since the Iranian revolution, the US’s main focus in the region has been to contain Iranian influence, guarantee Israel’s security, and protect access to oil resources. If the US historically relied on authoritarian Arab regimes to continue this influence and maintain the status quo, then the Arab Spring challenged the notion that regimes in the Arab world could ensure stability and uphold US interests. Then, the challenge of the Arab Spring was not only to the Arab world but also to the US foreign policy toward the region.

It seemed like American policy during the Obama administration was positively somehow interested in promoting democracy and freedom, as he had given the famous Cairo Speech on democracy at Cairo University, Cairo, in 2009. However, many scholars disagree and are uncomfortable with the argument of the US’s promotion of democracy.

Policy analysts say that American policy in the WANA region has never been historically pro-democratic, but strategic and geopolitical.

Michael Mc Faul (2004), a senior adviser to President Obama and scholar of democratisation and democracy promotion, wrote in his article "*Democracy Promotion as a World Value*" and argued that at the time of the Arab Spring, he wondered privately "why these sovereignty champions had been so quiet during decades of American subsidisation of Egyptian autocracy." Analysts such as Shadi Hamid (2015) have been similarly critical of the argument that the United States could not and should not influence post-Arab Spring events: "Where is the line between inaction and complicity? The notion of neutrality for a country as powerful as the United States is illusory. Doing nothing or 'not harm' means maintaining the status quo, which in the Middle East is never neutral, due to America's longstanding relationships with regional actors."

The US Contradictions of Supporting Undemocratic Regimes in the Region:

In the WANA region, the backlash against democracy promotion is described in two ways. First, the credibility of international actors, such as the United States, as champions of democracy and human rights has been severely compromised and even questioned. The US hypocrisy is not only very much visible but also very selective. First, they blamed Islamists for not giving up terror activities and radicalism. The US called on them to avoid these activities and participate in the democratic process. When Islamists participate in democratic politics and win the election, America and its Western allies do not recognise them.

In 2006, when Hamas won elections in Gaza, Palestine, with a thumping majority, Western powers did not acknowledge and declare Hamas a "terrorist organisation." The US was sharply criticised for applying a double standard in the 2006 Palestinian Parliamentary Elections while encouraging free and fair elections. But later, it decided to withdraw aid and diplomatically boycott the newly elected government when Hamas emerged as the victor. It is the same with the Muslim Brotherhood in Egypt, where they first supported and praised the Brotherhood members for their campaign against Mubarak and for respecting democratic values. However, the election happened, and the Brotherhood and its allied parties came into power; Americans became worried and felt threatened that they would no longer be able to protect their interest if

Islamists became strong in the region. The reason is clear: if Islamists came into power, the US interest and the security of Israel would be challenged in the region. The possibility of an Islamist rise to power via democratic means and potential opposition to Israel is an enduring concern for the American promotion of democracy. So, for the US, supporting authoritarian leaders and continuing their interests is a convenient and reasonable option. So, in both cases, we can see and analyse the situation when the US and its allies were challenged and refused to accept a democratically elected leader. It is well known to the US and its allies that public opinion in the WANA Region is not in their favour. So far, dealing with authoritarian and autocratic regimes is easier than an elected democratic government, which will be accountable to the people.

In opposition to the idea mentioned above about the takeover of democracy by Islamists, Laurie Mylroie (2008), an American thinker, suggests that democracy and Islamic tradition are incompatible and that illiberal Islamists may be worse than the current authoritarian regimes. However, she says it may be helpful in the US to promote human rights and democracy in certain parts of the WANA to oppose dictators. The other argument says the compatibility of democracy and the Islamic notion of Shura, or consultation. According to them, Western and international donors should not hesitate to promote democracy to encourage Arab democrats and responsible governance practices. Second, democracy promoters in the Arab world increasingly face competition from other regional and international actors who promote alternative democratic or openly authoritarian rule models. Beyond Russia and China's role, we can include regional players such as Saudi Arabia and Turkiye. As a result, the norms and how they are promoted are increasingly contested.

However, most states in the region have remained under authoritarian rule and thus continue to present real “complex cases” for promoting democracy. In the absence of a weak civil society and open resistance to external attempts to promote democracy, it is very difficult for external actors to promote democracy.

According to The Huffington Post, published in 2015, “The 45 nations with little or no democratic rule represent more than half of the roughly 80 countries now hosting US military bases.” The research is brought by

political scientist Kent Calder, who confirms and explains that in his “dictatorship hypothesis, “the United States offered to support dictators, authoritarian and other undemocratic regimes in the world where it enjoys basing facilities and advancing its interests.” This scepticism of democracy promotion and the view of aid has been seen as a dominant phenomenon in the region. US democracy promotion generally supports American regional interests instead of democratisation. Noam Chomsky (2007) argues that “US democratic rhetoric and undemocratic substance have a long history, and the US only supports democracy if and only if it conforms to US economic and strategic objectives.”

The US History of De-democratisation of the Region, Some Examples- Syria, Iran, Bahrain, Afghanistan, and Iraq:

Instead of democratising, the US has de-democratised the region after the Second World War. The US intelligence agency, CIA, was reported to be involved in a coup against the elected government of Syria in 1949. In the same way, a coup was also engineered by the US and the UK against democratic Iran in 1953. The US also subverted the possibility of democracy in Bahrain in the 1970s.

Syria:- Perhaps the earliest drama and facade of de-democratisation was Syria in the region. Imperial Britain and France defeated and divided the Ottoman Empire in the First World War. The imperial and colonial powers installed the Mandate System, an internationally sanctioned method of colonialism, also true to the logic of colonialism, under the agreement of the League of Nations in 1919. As a result, Syria came under French rule and only gained independence in 1946. While under French control, presidential elections happened in Syria, where a government was elected based on universal male suffrage. Shukri al-Quwatli came to power for a five-year term, which started in August 1943. After its independence, the elected government of Syria was based on a constitution and elected democracy. In March 1949, the US-led CIA managed a military coup against al-Quwatli’s government and removed it from power, and Colonel Husni al-Zaim installed had been installed, followed by the coup.

The US de-democratised Syria because al-Quwatli’s democratic government was nationalist and refused to toe the US line and informed that Syria would not adopt any policy against its security and sovereignty, even if “it meant defying America.” The US wanted Syria

to fulfil at least two of its several aims, which Colonel al-Zaim joyfully did. Syrian president Zaim legitimised Israel by signing an armistice and ratifying the TAPLINE (Trans-Arabian Pipeline Company) project, allowing ARAMCO (Arabian-American Oil Company) to pipe Saudi oil across Syria to the Mediterranean Sea. However, the Syrian parliament rejected both demands under a democratically elected government. Rejection was reportedly due to Western and US support for the partition of Palestine and the creation and support of the establishment of the State of Israel during the 1948 Arab-Israeli War. Between 1949, when al-Quwatli's democratic government was dislodged, and 1955, the US-led CIA organised five more coups.

Iran:- The next major de-democratisation was Iran, which was overthrown in 1953 by a US-UK alliance when Mohammad Mosaddeq was elected prime minister and received the approval of Iran's parliament for nationalising the oil and natural gas resources. The US and the UK organised a CIA-led coup to remove Mosaddeq because Iran refused to make cheap oil concessions to the West. During the Second World War, the UK took control of Iran and prevented oil from being passed to its ally, the Soviet Union. Even after the war, the UK continued to control Iran's oil through a British oil company named the Anglo-Iranian Oil Company. However, French-educated Iranian president Mosaddeq was undeterredly critical of Iranian natural resources utilised by the West. As a result, his popularity increased among the Iranian people. While facing Mosaddeq's popularity and resistance, the UK-US alliance orchestrated a coup to overthrow the government. The 1953 coup of Iran was also important for Central and South America to understand the regime change. Indeed, it soon became a model for regime change in the world. After a year, in 1954, the New York Times reported in 2000 that the CIA planned a successful coup in Guatemala.

Bahrain:- Another theatre of de-democratisation in West Asia was Bahrain. A country that was formerly a British protectorate and became independent in 1971. In December 1973, the first elections based on male franchise were organised to elect the thirty members of Al-Majlis Al-Watani, the National Assembly. After the elections, the national assembly challenged the al-Khalifa family's authority, which had ruled Bahrain since 1783. The assembly also demanded to leave the US Navy base in Bahrain. It should be noted that the US military presence in

Bahrain has been there since 1949 and increased after the withdrawal of British forces. Legally, Bahrain's assembly was correct in asking for the eviction of the US Navy. However, the ruling Al-Khalifas dissolved the group on August 26, 1975. There was then no democracy, as in 2002, on February 14, the Kingdom of Bahrain was declared, and hope for democracy became almost non-existent. Admiral William James Crowe Jr., an American Navy admiral and diplomat, justified the national assembly's dissolution, saying that "on general principles, the US Navy did not want to leave a place where they were already established." One may say there was no "external" intervention, and the Al-Khalifa family took a "sovereign internal" decision to dissolve the assembly.

Afghanistan:- The US de-democratisation continued in Afghanistan after the fall of the Taliban government. In November 2001, a UN-led conference was organised in Bonn, Germany, to decide Afghanistan's future. The objective was to promote democracy and women's freedom in Afghanistan. It was interesting to note that the Afghan representatives invited to Bonn, the leader Abdul Satar Sirat, elected by a majority of votes to lead the interim government, was asked to resign and brought to Hamid Karzai. However, the decision to install and promote "democracy" in Afghanistan was itself taken undemocratically. The reason was clear: the aim was not to install and promote democracy but to install Karzai, "our man", eager to pursue Western interests. Journalist James Fergusson, author of the book *"A Million Bullets and Taliban,"* had argued that Karzai was "absolutely not interested in the principles of democracy." The former Australian Prime Minister, John Howard, later admitted and expressed his intention that the West did not want to get involved in Afghanistan's reconstruction or any "nation-building." Surgical operations against the removal of the Taliban in Afghanistan were the key goal. However, the Taliban returned to power in 2021 after twenty years of US invasion and war in Afghanistan.

Iraq:- The story of de-democratisation was similar in Iraq following the US-led invasion of Iraq and the fall of the government in April 2003. The people in Iraq in various places, as diverse as Mosul, Samara, Hilla, Najaf, and Baghdad, organised meetings to elect their representatives for reconstruction, safety, and the provision of essential infrastructure. It was planned to elect the representatives of the various councils that had been made. However, the US prevented such democratic initiatives and nullified the decisions. The US appointed its own reliable and even unelected officials, including former Baathists. The whole drama and

“facade of democracy” were organised in such a way that the US would install democracy by toppling Saddam Hussein and creating an ideal for other countries in the region. However, it did not happen.

Conclusion:

Promoting democracy in the WANA region is laudable, as well as public discourse amongst American leaders. Nevertheless, it was never implemented in practice and became only an oral tokenism of a statement. The US policy towards the WANA region traditionally favoured and prioritised the stability of its friendly regimes. For the US, it does not matter how undemocratic or authoritarian the regime is, and it places much importance on its relations rather than the promotion of democratic change. However, the acceptance of the authoritarian regimes was justified based on the participation of security, the flow of oil without disruptions, gas, and other energy resources, so regime cooperation is necessary. Historical documents show that the US de-democratised some countries of the WANA region rather than promoting democracy, despite having a positive and golden opportunity for democracy promotion.

The study suggested that the US efforts to promote democracy failed because democracy needs to develop out of internal conditions and cannot be forcibly imposed from outside. There was disagreement about what constituted democracy; Drake suggested American leaders sometimes defined democracy in a narrow sense of a nation having elections, and, while needed, a broader understanding. Further, there was disagreement about what constituted a “rebellion”; Drake saw a pattern in which the US State Department disapproved of any rebellion, even so-called “revolutions” and, in some instances, revolts against dictatorships. The more severe criticism of American democracy promotion work in the WANA region is that it can lead to more harm than good.

By praising disingenuous reforms, the United States risks further entrenching dictatorship in the region. The Western power elites viewed the WANA region as a region of multiple resources like oil, natural gas, hydrocarbons, and strategic interests. Hence, they aim to remain “stable” and “manageable.” Ernest Bevin, former Member of Parliament and Foreign Secretary of Imperial Britain, once said that “without its oil and other potential resources,” there was “no hope of our being able to achieve the standard of life at which we are aiming in Great Britain.”

References

- America's Empire of Military Bases: How US Bases Back Dictators, Autocrats and Military Regimes - Toward Freedom. <https://towardfreedom.org/story/archives/globalism/americas-empire-military-bases-us-bases-back-dictators-autocrats-military-regimes/>.
- Ahmed, E. (2015). The Dilemma of Middle Eastern Democracy <https://www.e-ir.info/2015/10/04/the-dilemma-of-middle-eastern-democracy/>.
- Ahmad, I. (2012). How the West De-democratised the Middle East. Published in Al-Jazeera Opinion. <https://www.aljazeera.com/opinions/2012/3/30/how-the-west-de-democratised-the-middle-east>. (Accessed on 23rd October 2024).
- Bellin, E. (2004). The Robustness of Authoritarianism in the Middle East: Exceptionalism in Comparative Perspective. *Comparative Politics*, 36(2), 139–157. <https://doi.org/10.2307/4150140>.
- Chomsky, N. (2007). *Failed States: The Abuse of Power and the Assault on Democracy*. Metropolitan Books.
- Documents on Democracy | Journal of Democracy. <https://www.journalofdemocracy.com/articles/documents-on-democracy-4/>.
- Dunne, C. W. (2016). *Middle East Democracy: Recommendations for the Next President*. Middle East Institute. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep17597>.
- Democracy Promotion by the United States. (2024, June 3). In *Wikipedia*. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Democracy_promotion_by_the_United_States. (Accessed on November 11th, 2024).
- Drake, P. W. (2009). *Between Tyranny and Anarchy: A History of Democracy in Latin America, 1800-2006*. Stanford University Press.
- Falk, R. (2016). The US Will Not Pivot Away from the Middle East. Published in the Al-Jazeera Opinion. <https://www.aljazeera.com/opinions/2016/7/10/the-us-wont-pivot-away-from-the-middle-east>. (Accessed on 23rd October 2024).
- Heydarian, R. J. (2012). The Western Hypocrisy in the Middle East Allows China to Falsely Present Itself as a Defender of the Muslim World. Published in Al-Jazeera Opinion. <https://www.aljazeera.com/opinions/2021/6/10/china-is-exploiting-western-hypocrisy-in-the-middle-east>. (Accessed on 23rd October 2024).
- Hobson, C. (2005). A Forward Strategy of Freedom in the Middle East: US Democracy Promotion and the 'War on Terror'. *Australian Journal of International Affairs*, 59(1), 39–53.
- Hüllen, Vera Van, and Peace Research Institute Frankfurt Report (2018). "Democracy Promotion in the Arab World." Democracy Promotion in Times of Uncertainty: Trends and Challenges. <https://www.ssoar.info/ssoar/bitstream/handle/document/59980/ssoar-2018-Democracy>

The US Promotion of Democracy in the Wana Region: Myth vs. Reality –Kalam

[Promotion in Times of.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y&lnkname=ssolar-2018-Democracy Promotion in Times of.pdf.](#)

- Hoben, A. (1989). USAID: Organisational and Institutional Issues and Effectiveness. *Cooperation for International Development: The United States and the Third World in the 1990s*, 253–278.
- Hassan, Oz. “Bush’s Freedom Agenda: Ideology and the Democratization of the Middle East.” *Democracy and Security* 4, No. 3 (2008): 268–89. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48602627>.
- How US Military Bases Abroad Undermine National Security and Harm Us All. Published in The HuffPost on September 13th, 2015, by David Vine. https://www.huffpost.com/entry/us-military-bases-abroad_b_8131402. (Accessed on November 1, 2024).
- Interview with Condoleezza Rice by James Harding and Richard Wolffe, *Financial Times*, September 23, 2002.
- Ibrahim, S. E. (2007). Toward Muslim Democracies. *Journal of Democracy*, 18(2), 5-13.
- Lahlou-Kassi, A. (2014). International Livestock Research Institute: Mandate, Programme and Potential Contribution to Rangeland Improvement in the WANA Region.
- Monshipouri, M. & Ali, A. (2011). The New Middle East and the United States, What to Expect After the Uprising. Published in the Insight Turkey. <https://www.insightturkey.com/articles/the-new-middle-east-and-the- united-states-what-to-expect-after-the-uprisings>. (Accessed on 23rd October 2024).
- Neep, D. (2004). Dilemmas of Democratisation in The Middle East: The “Forward Strategy of Freedom”. *Middle East Policy*, 11(3), 73–84.
- Nader Hashemi, The Arab Spring, The US Foreign Policy, and the Question of Democracy in the Middle East, 41 *Denv. J. Int'l L. & Poly* 31 (2012). <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/djilp>.
- Obama Administration Commends Egypt for Orderly Transition. (2011). *Foreign Policy Bulletin*, 21(2), 3–11. https://doi.org/10.1017/s1052703611000220_20.
- Ottaway, Marina. “Promoting Democracy In The Middle East: The Problem of US Credibility.” *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, 2003. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep12977>.
- Syria, Egypt, and the Arab Spring: How US Policy Failed the Middle East - The Atlantic. <https://www.theatlantic.com/international/archive/2015/10/middle-east-egypt-us-policy/409537/>.
- Sharp, J. M., & Humud, C. E. (2005, June). US Foreign Assistance to the Middle East: Historical Background, Recent Trends, and the FY2006 Request. Congressional Research Service, the Library of Congress.

- The Middle East and North Africa in the 21st Century - History Guild. <https://historyguild.org/the-middle-east-and-north-africa-in-the-21st-century/>.
- The UN Arab Human Development Report (2004). Towards Freedom in the Arab World. <https://hdr.undp.org/system/files/documents/rbasahdr2004en.pdf>.
- The US Democracy Promotion in the Arab World: Beyond Interests vs. Ideals Mieczysław p. Boduszyński Lynne Rienner Publishers Website www.rienner.com.
- The Muslim Brotherhood and Egypt's Succession Crisis: The Politics of Liberalisation and Reform in the Middle East 9780755607877, 9781845119799 - DOKUMEN.PUB. <https://dokumen.pub/the-muslim-brotherhood-and-egypts-succession-crisis-the-politics-of-liberalisation-and-reform-in-the-middle-east-9780755607877-9781845119799.html>.
- Talei, Rafiah A. (2021). The Dilemma of US Democracy and Human Rights Promotion in the Middle East. <https://carnegieendowment.org/sada/2021/05/the-dilemma-of-us-democracy-and-human-rights-promotion-in-the-middle-east?lang=en>.
- Wang, J., & Wang, S. (2008). The Middle Eastern Democratization in the Context of Anti-Americanism. *Journal of Middle Eastern and Islamic Studies (in Asia)*, 2(1), 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19370679.2008.12023111>.
- Yıldırım, Y. The US Foreign Aid to Middle East and North Africa in Bush and Obama Era. *Journal of Middle East Perspectives*, 1(2), 79–116.
- Zahid, M. (2007). Economic and Political Liberalisation in the Middle East: The Muslim Brotherhood and Succession Politics in Egypt. <https://core.ac.uk/download/375530916.pdf>.